

Finding Ways to Be Lawyers in Today's World, Calling to Have the Courage to Make Changes. Mindfulness Matters: Thought, Attention, Awakening.

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Abstract

Legal style of life is to remain in constant flux. Legal professionals are finding ways to be lawyers in today's world. The leading legal experts examine the results of COP26, discussing the advancements and setbacks in COP26 from the perspective of their disciplines, research agendas, and regions. Lawyers will be 'more in demand than ever', says Sir Geoffrey Vos, November 4, 2021. The central premise of the paper is that the twenty-first century presents new challenges to the judiciary/lawyers: human cloning, computer data mining, computer-generated judicial profiles, smart, online courts systems etc on one side, and the era of globalization, digitilisation of society, terror, ecology catastrophe, human rights protection crisis, poverty, new diseases (Covid-19 etc) on another side, are obvious examples. Scholars' pragmatism, with its emphasis on "what works," might fill the legal void when new challenges arise. But precisely what are the general solutions available to the lawmaker, lawyers and the judiciary? Could we offer the receipt, suitable for any nation, any state? We forward these questions for discussion, attracting the readers's attention to the role of Mindfulness, Discretion, Creativity, Thought, Attention, Awakening in a legal job. Calling to have the courage to make changes, the paper is seeking the answers in quantum physics/mechanics.

Keywords: judge, lawyer, crisis, energy, wave, quantum theory, granularity, probability, observations, complexity, thought, attention, awakening.

While no industry seems to have been spared the impact brought on by the crisis, legal professionals have a particularly hard time coping with crisis-related challenges.
Legal style of life is to remain in constant flux. Being lawyer is being in movement. Being lawyer means the movement and doesn't mean certain working conditions; means the pathway and doesn't mean a harbor.

Today the leading legal experts examine the results of COP26, discussing the advancements and setbacks in COP26 from the perspective of their disciplines, research agendas, and regions.

COP26 ended with the agreement of the Glasgow Climate Pact by all the 197 nations at the conference. According to the UK Presidency's press release, the pact will "keep 1.5C alive and finalise the outstanding elements of the Paris Agreement."¹

COP president Alok Sharma described the pact as a "fragile win." He emphasised that its long-term success will require countries to "meet and deliver on the commitments"² they have agreed.

As has been widely reported, the pact has left many nations unhappy, not least because of a last-minute change of the drafting on coal and fossil fuel subsidies. The fact that they were prepared to endorse it reflects the general sense of the conference that an agreement – even if clearly imperfect – was vital.

In the words of UN Secretary-General António Guterres: "The approved texts are a compromise. They reflect the interests, the conditions, the contradictions and the state of

1 <https://cms.law/en/gbr/insight/cop26>

2 Ibid

political will in the world today. They take important steps, but unfortunately the collective political will was not enough to overcome some deep contradictions.”³

‘Loss and damage’ is another section of the Glasgow Climate Pact that left many delegates disappointed. There is to be a dialogue (the ‘the Glasgow Dialogue between Parties, relevant organizations and stakeholders’) on funding support for vulnerable nations that are already suffering the effects of climate change. But the proposed creation of a facility to help pay for loss and damage, present in an earlier draft of the agreement, was rejected by various developed nations.

Possibly the clearest ‘wins’ for COP26 were the agreement of rules on carbon markets and a tightening of the Paris ‘ratchet’ mechanism to speed up the toughening of national plans to reduce emissions.

The clearest consequence of COP26 is that lawyers will be ‘more in demand than ever’ (following Sir Geoffrey Vos’s words⁴). He confirmed that lawyers will ‘continue to be engaged wherever they can add value’. Sir Geoffrey Vos also added the changes will ‘probably come quickly and be more radical than any of us can imagine’.⁵

The central premise of this news is that the twenty-first century presents new challenges to the judiciary/lawyers – challenges which may sometimes leave existing law and procedure in a kind of limbo. Human cloning, computer data mining, computer-generated judicial profiles, online dispute resolution (smart, online court systems) etc on one side, and the era of globalization, digitalization, terror, human rights protection catastrophe, poverty, climate change, new diseases (Covid-19 etc) on another side, are obvious examples.

Legal work — and litigation especially — requires a great deal of mental stamina, whether it’s related to meeting unforgiving deadlines, juggling high-pressure demands from clients, preparing for an intensive, high-stakes trial, or just keeping up with the fast-paced environment of busy firms and growing practices. When most of one’s work is accompanied by a significant mental strain, there will always be a risk of negative impacts on their mental health. The pandemic has only complicated efforts within courts and law firms to address these issues, and we keep that in mind when evaluating the efficacy of current treatment and support methods.

The topic is itself moving target. Over the next decades, judges/lawyers will be required to apply laws to radically different circumstances and in radically new environment as a result of a new era we can only begin to imagine. Global threats, political, environmental, epidemic, will put immense stress on the legal institutions. The unpredictable and unprecedented nature of such developments makes all analyses of justice/lawyering highly provisional, but also necessary, and as it turned out, highly stimulating. It’s a matter of the rule of law, to fulfill our role of stewardship by insulating justice/legal principles against the challenges of the future.

Scholars’ pragmatism, with its emphasis on “what works,” might fill the legal void when new challenges arise. But precisely what are the general solutions available to the lawmaker, the judiciary, the legal professionals? Could we offer the receipt, suitable for any nation, any state? We’re seeking the answers in quantum physics/mechanics.

The treatment we offer consists of *Mindfulness Approach*. The truth is that we, in fact, are showing an increased dedication to judges/lawyers/society’s (mental) well-being.

³ Ibid

⁴ <https://www.lawgazette.co.uk/news/lawyers-will-be-more-in-demand-than-ever-with-online-courts-says-vos/5110434.article>

⁵ Ibid

Perhaps one thing the pandemic has taught us is that we need to reimagine what our workdays look like, regardless of our industry. As challenges related to the pandemic can be avoided more strategically, the real value of our treatment should begin to come into focus. "Justice is an art.." ⁶ - said Prof. Louis B. Schwartz in the Owen J. Roberts Memorial Lecture, given at the University of Pennsylvania on October 9, 1986. And we agree. Justice/good lawyering is an art, a symbol, an energy.

Symbols are a language of allegory, created long before the lettered words we are imprisoned by today. "A picture tells a thousand words" ⁷. Combined with oral tradition, symbols are just as effective at containing and recalling information as any computer – possibly more so.

Let's begin with the *Wanderer above the Sea of Fog* by Caspar David Friedrich to receive some information from it.

The image has been used on the cover of numerous books, as a signifier of mystery, *inter alia*. We use it as a signifier of justice/good lawyering. Judge/lawyer is the wanderer on the roads of justice/good lawyering. It is the message conveyed by the painting is one of Kantian self-reflection, meditation, expressed through the lawyer/judge/wanderer's gazings into the justice/good lawyering that is the sea of fog for everyone, at the start of trial/case. ⁸ Judge/wanderer presents a metaphor for the unknown justice in a pending suit. ⁹ The impression the lawyer/judge/wanderer's position atop the precipice and before the unmindful outlook leaves is sure, suggesting at once mastery over a landscape of law and mind, the insignificance of the individual judging within it. ¹⁰ It is what a judge/lawyer sees inside himself. Friedrich states his ideas in regards to this, "The artist should paint not only what he has in front of him but also what he sees inside himself." ¹¹

Let's turn to *The Starry Night* by Vincent van Gogh. Van Gogh's "Starry Night" is very similar not only to the exact mathematical description of turbulent air flows in the Earth's atmosphere, but also to the supersonic vortices of gas and dust in the "stellar nursery". This is the conclusion reached by scientists who published an article in the arXiv.org electronic library.

"We have shown that 'Starry Night' resembles real turbulence, which directly affects the way we see stars at night. At the same time, the nature of the distribution of energy in the vortices in the picture suggests that it very accurately reflects how the flows behave gas in dense "gas and dust" nebulae, where new stars are born," ¹² - the scientists write.

Art as energy shows that a thing is as it is, does what it does, means what it means. Art as energy implies a person giving attention. How much attention one can give is a problem of energy.

Justice/lawyering is an energy. Judge/lawyer attracts and sends energy.

⁶ Schwartz Louis B. Justice and Other Non-Economic Goals of Antitrust, 127 U. Pa. L. Rev. 1076 (1979). Available at: <https://scholarship.law>

⁷ Henrik Ibsen, a Norwegian playwright and theatre director, first said "A thousand words leave not the same deep impression as does a single deed." After his death in 1906 this quote was plagiarized and para-phrased into what we know now.

⁸ Following the analysis of Gorra, Michael Edward in: *The Bells in Their Silence: Travels Through Germany*. Princeton University Press, 11-12 (2004), <https://archive.org/details/bellsintheirsile00gorr/page/11/mode/2up>

⁹ Following the analysis of Dembo, Ron S; Freeman, Andrew in: *The Rules of Risk: A Guide for Investors*, Wiley, 10 (January 19, 2001)

¹⁰ Following the analysis of Gaddis, John Lewis in: *The Landscape of History. The Landscape of History: How Historians Map the Past*. Oxford University Press. 1-2. (2004)

¹¹ *Wanderer Above the Sea of Fog*, Caspar David Friedrich (Ca. 1817). Scholastic Art, <https://www.the-artists.org/wanderer-above-the-sea-of-fog/>

¹² <https://arxiv.org/abs/1902.03381>

Quantum physics is applicable to a legal job. But it seems that modern judges/lawyers vote for classical physics.

Classical physics teaches that the universe is mechanistic and that everything is separate. According to a materialistic conception, the physical world represents the only *reality*, precisely because it is tangible and measurable. This is the belief that people have based their lives upon for centuries – and this belief has been limiting their experiences and their possibilities. The scientists who investigate and seek have only lifted the veil of a corner of reality, everything else remains unknown, indeed the more we discover the greater depths unfold before us. Unfathomable mystery surrounds and envelops us. Pavel Florensky¹³ spoke of *the invisible*¹⁴, Niels Bohr¹⁵ - of *the implicit order*.¹⁶ Quantum physics is revealing that classical physics isn't explaining what we now know about *reality*. Among other things – there is an energy field from which everything emerges. The *seen* emerges from the *unseen*.

“If you want to find the secrets of the universe, think in terms of energy, frequency and vibration”¹⁷, -Nikola Tesla¹⁸ said. Following them, if a judge/lawyer wants to comprehend the secrets of changing world, law, he/she has *to think in terms of energy, frequency, vibration, seen and unseen*.

Here are some of the interesting and radical concepts and ideas that are emerging from quantum physics. If every judge/lawyer would really get what the scientists are now saying about *the nature of reality* – judicial/legal practice would change dramatically!! And it would free a man up to have dynamic and fulfilling right to live in abundance; rather than to struggle or suffer.

-What physics has discovered is that everything is energy and that this energy is everywhere – in space and in matter.

-There is no such thing as empty space. It is filled with energy.

-This energy seems to be *aware* – it responds to consciousness and is affected by the thoughts or energy of the observer. Physics now says there is no way to prove an objective reality because the observer always affects the outcome of the experiment.¹⁹

-Everything is connected. We are all one. Nothing is separate from this field of energy. This is what mystics, spiritual masters, and indigenous people have taught for a long time.

-All That Is/Universal Intelligence/God – whatever name you want to call this – is omnipotent, omniscient, and omnipresent. Omnipresent means present everywhere. There is NO place he isn't. So whatever *Universal Intelligence* is – it is everywhere.

13 Pavel Aleksandrovich Florensky (1882-1937) was a Russian Orthodox theologian, priest, philosopher, mathematician, physicist, electrical engineer, inventor, polymath and neomartyr.

14 <http://www.novaeuropa.it/prodotto/lestetica-dellinvisibile-il-pensiero-eurasiatico-di-pavel-florenskij/>

15 Niels Henrik David Bohr (1885-1962) was a Danish physicist who made foundational contributions to understanding atomic structure and quantum theory, for which he received the Nobel Prize in Physics in 1922. Bohr was also a philosopher and a promoter of scientific research.

16 <https://blogs.scientificamerican.com/cross-check/david-bohm-quantum-mechanics-and-enlightenment/>

17 <https://www.forbes.com/sites/davidbressan/2020/01/07/nikola-teslas-earthquake-machine/>

18 Nikola Tesla (1856-1943) was a Serbian-American inventor, physicist, and electrical engineer. His life's work is characterized by numerous innovations in the field of electrical engineering, especially in electrical energy technology, such as the development of the system for electrical energy transmission, now known as two-phase alternating current. Tesla has received over 280 patents in 26 countries, 112 of them in the United States.

19 Check out the research being done at Princeton University around the Random Number Generator. They are working to see how consciousness affects the results of experiments. Also check out the research being done around consciousness at the Institute of Noetic Sciences.

Darwin had the dilemma, appeared from the 1870s letter to Joseph D. Hooker²⁰: “I cannot look at the universe as the result of blind chance. However, I cannot see evidence of a benevolent design, or indeed of a design of any kind, in detail.”²¹ At the end of his life, the evolutionary scientist is not certain - he cannot be - that the engine of evolution is chance; too many other findings say this is not the case. But he cannot see a drawing, also; many other findings say that there is not something precise that happens in this immense movement in which we were born. In short, no theory can be built, neither “the radiant one of creationism nor the dark one of atheism”, says Vito Mancuso²². He concludes: “We are sent back to the impossibility of a vision of the world as knowing”. We know nothing, only hypotheses, more or less sensible arguments. What is certain is that we are moving towards something more, which shows a final perfection. However, there is a direction. Here is what Darwin writes again: “And since natural selection works exclusively through and for the good of each being, all bodily and psychic enrichments will tend to progress towards perfection.”²³

Carlo Rovelli²⁴ writes on the strange phenomenas: they have one thing in common: they highlight a curious granularity of energy and other physical quantities. Before the quantum no one suspects that energy could be granular.²⁵ It was Einstein who suggested that light and all other electromagnetic waves are made up of elementary *grains*, each with a fixed energy, which depends on frequency. Today we call them photons, the quanta of light. Einstein manages to explain a phenomenon not understood at the time. Called the photoelectric effect, and predicting its characteristics before they are measured. Einstein was the first to realize that the problems raised by these phenomena are so serious that they require a revision of the entire mechanics.²⁶ This makes him the spiritual father of quantum theory. His idea that light is a wave but also a cloud of photons is confusing, but it is the idea that inspires de Broglie to think that all elementary particles are waves²⁷ and then Schrödinger to introduce the *wave*.²⁸ Einstein is therefore the inspirer of quantum mechanics in several ways: Born learns from him that mechanics must be completely revised; Heisenberg is inspired by him in restricting attention to measurable quantities only; Schrödinger starts from de Broglie's idea inspired by Einstein's photons. What's more: Einstein is also the first to study atomic phenomena using probability, thus putting Born on the road to understanding that the meaning of the wave Ψ is a probability. The construction of quantum theory was a team game.

20 Sir Joseph Dalton Hooker (1817–1911) was a British botanist and explorer in the 19th century. He was a founder of geographical botany and Charles Darwin's closest friend.

21 More letters of Charles Darwin, edited by F. Darwin, A. C. Seward, vol. 1, 321 (1903).

22 Vito Mancuso (1962) is an Italian theologian and teacher.

23 Darwin Charles, *The origin of species*, Newton Compton, 511 (1994)

24 Carlo Rovelli is an internationally renowned theoretical physicist who during his career has worked mainly in the field of quantum gravity and was one of the founders of the theory of loop quantum gravity. Carlo Rovelli also deals with the history and philosophy of science. In *Helgoland* Rovelli delves into revolutionary theory, first allowing us to understand its theoretical and practical value, and then exploring the issues that make quantum theory one of the most mysterious physical theories science has to do with. These mysteries have been at the center of the research of physicists, philosophers and other great thinkers for years: Rovelli focuses on the relational interpretation and on the links between this interpretation and oriental history, art, literature and philosophy. The author leads to discover how this view of quantum theory can lead us to reconsider the way in which we think about reality.

25 <https://spazio-tempo-luce-energia.it/tempo-e-meccanica-quantistica-1629d269e561>

26 In March 1905, Einstein — still a lowly patent clerk in Switzerland — published a paper explaining the photoelectric effect.

27 De Broglie's hypothesis of matter waves postulates that any particle of matter that has linear momentum is also a wave. See in detail: <https://www.thoughtco.com/de-broglie-hypothesis-2699351>

28 The Schrödinger equation is a linear partial differential equation that governs the wave function of a quantum-mechanical system. See in detail: https://www.tcm.phy.cam.ac.uk/~bds10/aqp/handout_foundations.pdf

The name of quantum theory comes from *grains*. Quantum phenomena reveal a granular aspect of the world on a very small scale. Granularity is not just about energy: it is extremely general. In Rovelli's field of study, quantum gravity, it is shown that the physical space in which we live is granular at a very small scale. *Granularity* is the third key conceptual ingredient of quantum theory, alongside *probability* and *observations*.²⁹ It is physical reality that passions and preferred world views often cloud one's judgement, biasing this or that goal with a sense of purpose that is undeservedly deemed unique or unavoidable. We are most blind at the end of knowledge, the boundary between knowing and not-knowing.

We base on well-established ideas from the *complexity theory*.³⁰

*Complexity*³¹ is a way of reality's being. The complexity of contemporary world presents many challenges at different levels.

The reality is complex, it is articulated. Therefore it is necessary to find a way, a strategy to deal with it. A judge/lawyer needs to have a new mentality that accepts to abandon the securities. Simplifying is not good. The world is made up of a great deal of interactions (biological and social). Knowing does not eliminate ignorance. Scientists know this well, they see infinite problems open up as soon as they solve one.

The discovery of complexity, which took place thanks to computers that made it possible to reproduce the complex that exists in nature, is one of the most important achievements in knowledge of the world: a science that has revolutionized the way a man sees things and asks himself about them. As for evolution it is not a theory, but a way of being of the real, of all the real, even and above all what a man has inside him, the world of biology. Indeed it was this world that made the most important steps in the field. It is interesting to know how scientists, step by step, have advanced in these discoveries, a completely unknown area. Complexity includes chaos, network science, statistics. If a man considers that quantum mechanics has discovered the relationship, the system, the networks at the basis of reality, he comprehends that he is in possession of a really important knowledge. Werner

29 More details: Rovelli Carlo, Helgoland (2020); Rovelli Carlo, Unfinished revolution (2008), <https://arxiv.org/pdf/gr-qc/0604045.pdf>

30 Complexity Theory allows us to better understand systems as diverse as cells, human beings, forest ecosystems, and organizations, that are only partially understood by traditional scientific methods (Zimmerman, B. Complexity Science: A Route through Hard Times and Uncertainty. Health Forum Journal 42-46 (March/April 1999); Zimmerman, B. Lindberg C. and Plsek P. Edgware: Insights from Complexity Science or Health Care Leaders. Irving Texas: VHA, Inc, (1998.). While it represents a relatively nascent field of study, it spans across a wide variety of disciplines in the physical, biological, and social sciences, and has profound implications for the way we think about and act within the world (Schneider, M&Somers,M. Organizations as complex adaptive systems: Implications of Complexity Theory for leadership research. The Leadership Quarterly, 17(4), 351–365(2006): <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2006.04.006>).

31 Complexity characterises the behaviour of a system or model whose components interact in multiple ways and follow local rules, meaning there is no reasonable higher instruction to define the various possible interactions (See: Johnson Steven, Emergence: The Connected Lives of Ants, Brains, Cities. New York: Scribner, 19 (2001) Neil Johnson states that *even among scientists, there is no unique definition of complexity – and the scientific notion has traditionally been conveyed using particular examples*, (Johnson Neil F, Chapter 1: Two's company, three is complexity, in Simply complexity: A clear guide to complexity theory (2009), <https://web.archive.org/web/20151211064454/http://www.uvm.edu/rsenr/nr385se/readings/complexity.pdf> In several scientific fields, *complexity* has a precise meaning.

Heisenberg³² was sure, existing scientific concepts always embrace only a limited part of reality, while the other part, that still misunderstood, is infinite.³³³⁴

What physicists have discovered is this *field* of energy, a field of all possibilities – until an Understanding complexity means understanding that it is not possible to have total knowledge, so it is necessary to accept all arguments, even the most contradictory ones, to try to connect, not to incorporate.

Edgar Morin³⁵ says: “from the start, complex thought is aware of the impossibility of complete knowledge: one of the axioms of complexity is the impossibility of even theoretical omniscience. ... I have always aspired to multidimensional thinking. ... I have always felt that some profound truths, antagonistic to each other, were complementary for me, without ceasing to be antagonistic”³⁶ It is wrong to think that it is necessary to simplify, that it is possible to arrive at a single doctrine, and that everything can be rationalized. We need to develop a theory, a logic and an epistemology of complexity that can be adapted to the knowledge; at the same time to seek the unity of science and the theory of the highest human complexity. We need a non-totalitarian, theoretical but not doctrinal, multidimensional discourse, open to uncertainty and overcoming; not ideal/idealistic, knowing that the thing will never be totally enclosed in the concept, the world will never be imprisoned in the discourse. This is the idea of a new science.

We share the idea of Morin, complexity is the challenge, it is not the answer observer measures it or focuses on it. So mindfulness (consciousness) seems to be intrinsically connected with this field of all possibilities.

“Judges/lawyers are literally creating (or co-creating) their own reality along with this energy. Judges/lawyers like to imagine the infinite, the unknown, that surrounds and invades them. Judges/lawyers like to get lost in it as poets did.” -We think this is the most important and true position for judges/lawyers. We think this is the wisest way to apply discretion/creativity, to resolve the disputes, to find the legal solutions, not neglecting the commitment to reach their fullness because they can *shipwreck* with all of themselves in that infinity. Positive immersion, contemplation that completes are the most important things. This paper attempts to show one counter-intuitive consequence of the complexity, taking into account that science is beginning to recognize the reality of intuition, where it comes from and how natural it is within all of us.³⁷

What can judges/lawyers learn from the rise of post-material science?

Quantum physics is challenging and revising what judges/lawyers have believed about *reality*.

32 Werner Karl Heisenberg (1901–1976) was a German theoretical physicist and one of the key pioneers of quantum mechanics. He published his work in 1925 in a breakthrough paper. In the subsequent series of papers with Max Born and Pascual Jordan, during the same year, this matrix formulation of quantum mechanics was substantially elaborated. He is known for the uncertainty principle, which he published in 1927. Heisenberg was awarded the 1932 Nobel Prize in Physics *for the creation of quantum mechanics*.

33 See: Pangle Thomas L, On Heisenberg's Key Statement Concerning Ontology, *The Review of Metaphysics* Vol. 67, No. 4, 835-859 (JUNE 2014), <https://www.jstor.org/stable/24636444>

34 See Morin Edgar, *On Complexity* (2008)

35 Edgar Morin (1921) is a French philosopher and sociologist who has been internationally recognized for his work on complexity and *complex thought* (*pensée complexe*), and for his scholarly contributions to such diverse fields as media studies, politics, sociology, visual anthropology, ecology, education, and systems biology. He holds degrees in history, economics, and law.

36 https://tantestorie.weebly.com/uploads/3/8/8/3/38831493/pensiero_complesso.pdf

37 See here: https://www.collective-evolution.com/2018/05/26/scientists-explain-how-intuition-may-be-the-highest-form-of-intelligence/?fbclid=IwAR0n-oYlw4ASvNAew_TmxOQARQtNvBdkQ8cZErtoPIe9e7JbaWwzcFwVS4

It is common knowledge that the law is a linguistic proposition that has to be *interpreted*. Each judge is always obliged to make a judgment, even in cases of vagueness, ambiguity, imprecision, incompleteness of the law.³⁸ The judge is continually called upon to “translate” the text of the statute in decisions. Interpretation is a complex and dialectical system. The resolution of a legal dispute is something of procedural, which is based conceptually on three distinct steps: recognition of problem, research of rule to apply, effective application of a norm to issue.³⁹

Essentially the legal sciences aspire to establish a true “rational rigour”, different from that of mathematics, but no less necessary.⁴⁰ In this context, hermeneutics is configured as the “*workshop of living law*”.⁴¹ Every interpretative act is always inserted within a specific “living law”. The “living law” is a “dialectical synthesis” that incrementally is formed during repeated interpretations of the legal texts. Law, in absolute and general terms, collects the norms of a legal system (“*positive law*”) and the concrete application of these same rules in the judicial context (“*living law*”). The “living law” is crystallized in the “precedents”, in a whole of acts (sentences, ordinances, decrees, etc.) emanated by jurisdictional organs (courts).

Every judge, far from being a “*merely mouthpiece of the law*”, through his interpretation of the formal norms, contributes to the continuing realization of the “living law”.⁴²

Interpreting and applying the legal norms, judge/lawyer thinks and applies *the discretion/creativity*. In our days the discretion is the cornerstone of courts’ activity as the decision-making tool is a cornerstone of democracy. Judicial discretion appears as something questionable because the discretion can lead a judge to justice or injustice.⁴³

Judicial discretion/legal creativity consist of thoughts. So, *what is judge/lawyer’s thought and how does it connect up with justice/good lawyering?*

*Discretio est discernere per legem quid sit justum*⁴⁴, - Latin wisdom says.

Applying the quantum mechanics, Peter Baksa⁴⁵ confirms that our brain is comprised of a tight network of nerve cells, all interacting with one another and generating an overall electrical field. Our brain waves are simply the superposition of the multitude of electrical states being formed by our nervous system. Not only our brain, but our entire body has an electric field. Anywhere there's a nerve cell, there's electricity. It's just concentrated the greatest around our head because that's where the bulk of our nerve cells are. So, nothing mysterious about that part.

Being an electric field, all those overlying electric wave patterns that comprise our brain waves are governed by the same equations governing the electromagnetic spectrum, light, particles and everything else in the universe. The light seen coming from a star and the energy of our mind are one and the same type.

Our thoughts are formed in this electric field. Judge/lawyer’s thoughts are formed in this electric field. The measurable perturbations and disturbances in the brain's overall electric

38 Marinelli V. Studi sul diritto vivente, Jovene, Napoli, (2008).

39 Pascuzzi G. Giuristi si diventa, Il Mulino, Bologna, 85 (2008).

40 Marinelli V, Opt.cit.8.

41 Ibid.

42 See in: Bobbio, N, Il positivismo giuridico, Giappichelli, Torino (1979); Cappelletti M. Giudici legislatori?, Giuffrè, Milano, (1984).

43 Papkova O. Judicial Discretion (2005), 152.

44 Discretion is to discern through law what is just. Discretion in legal practice means the equitable decision of what is just and proper under the circumstances. It is the power of a judge, in certain matters, to decide in accordance with his own judgment of the equities for the cases, unhampered by inflexible rules of law. The latitude allowed to judges as to the action to be taken on certain facts.

45 <https://peterbaksa.com/huffington-post-peter-baksa>

field are our actual thoughts racing through our mind. The thoughts a judge/lawyer is thinking of, the words his mind is processing, are all electrical impulses. So thoughts are energy, the same as everything else.

That means they are governed by the rules of quantum mechanics and Schrödinger's⁴⁶ wave equations as well. All those same weird things about quantum mechanics that describe how an electron or photon behave, apply to a judge\lawmaker⁴⁷, to a lawyer, to anyone and to their thoughts as well. The particle-wave duality,⁴⁸ the uncertainty principle,⁴⁹ and of course, entanglement.⁵⁰

This implies that, like any other set of particles or source of energy, a judge/lawyer is entangled with everything he/she has ever encountered in hearings, in judiciary, in lawyering and the rest of the universe through *the zero point field*. We can think, we are conscious. As such, a judge/lawyer can choose which of the possibilities before him/her to collapse his/her wave function into. But more than that, a judge/lawyer can thus affect that as well and influence the randomness, just as it can influence him/her.

Since a judge/lawyer is conscious, he/she can choose what part of the randomness around him/her to be affected by, and how he/she in turn would like to affect it. It is through the property of entanglement that a judge/lawyer can affect change. Our minds are transceivers, able to receive and send signals into the "quantum soup" of the zero point field by way of the highly coherent frequencies of our thoughts.

The higher the frequency of lawyer\judge's thought\brain wave, the higher his/her consciousness. The level of his/her consciousness is what makes lawyer\judge's reality what it is and what it will continue to be..

The level of his/her consciousness (the frequency of lawyer\judge's thought\brain wave) is what makes his\her reality.

Peter Baksa⁵¹ writes: if you are seeking change, set an intention, declare a path (align your behaviors with your desire), then detach and allow the universe to handle the details. What is why the judge/lawyer's thought is very important for achieving justice/good lawyering.

46 One of the greatest physicists of 20th Century, Erwin Schrödinger is known for having a large breath of interests in non-physical disciplines, including biology and philosophy. In particular, his long essay from 1944, *What is Life?*, has been often mentioned in this respect. Schrödinger's ideas about the structure of material carrier of life, in particular of genetic information, and his ideas about living organisms feeding upon their negative entropy has greatly influenced quite a few prominent biologists of the time. Somewhat less known are his thoughts about the nature of consciousness and the Self included in the same essay as well as in his other works and lectures.

47 Legislator is a synonym of lawmaker. Lawmaker is a synonym of legislator. As nouns the difference between lawmaker and legislator is that lawmaker is one who makes or enacts laws while legislator is someone who creates or enacts laws, especially a member of a legislative body. Judge could be a lawmaker, doing conscious decision-making. See in detail: Bingham Tom, *The Business of Judging. Selected Essays and Speeches* (2000).

48 Wave-particle duality is the concept in quantum mechanics that every particle or quantum entity may be described as either a particle or a wave. It expresses the inability of the classical concepts "particle" or "wave" to fully describe the behaviour of quantum-scale objects. As Albert Einstein wrote: "It seems as though we must use sometimes the one theory and sometimes the other, while at times we may use either. We are faced with a new kind of difficulty. We have two contradictory pictures of reality; separately neither of them fully explains the phenomena of light, but together they do." (Einstein Albert, Infeld Leopold. *The Evolution of Physics: The Growth of Ideas from Early Concepts to Relativity and Quanta*, Cambridge University Press (1938) <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/1938epgi.book.....E/abstract>

49 Heisenberg's uncertainty principle is a key principle in quantum mechanics. Very roughly, it states that if we know everything about where a particle is located (the uncertainty of position is small), we know nothing about its momentum (the uncertainty of momentum is large), and vice versa. Versions of the uncertainty principle also exist for other quantities as well, such as energy and time. <https://www.britannica.com/science/uncertainty-principle>

50 Quantum entanglement is a quantum mechanical phenomenon in which the quantum states of two or more objects have to be described with reference to each other, even though the individual objects may be spatially separated.

51 Peter Baksa has written *The Point of Power, It's None of My Business What You Think of Me!, Thinking Yourself Young*, which will include interviews with Tibetan Monks from earlier this spring, and *The Faith Wave; I think therefore it is*, release date Jan 2012.

Ante omnia, a lawyer\judge has to pay attention to his/her thoughts as a part of judicial discretion\legal creativity centered on the theory of the separation of powers, on the Rule of Law, and other legal foundations.

Just the things we pay attention to are alive and the things that do not receive our attention die. It is applicable to everything, to every situation, to every person. It is applicable to Justice, to trial, to a judge\lawmaker, to a lawyer. It can be explained by quantum mechanics.

The crux of the Law of Attraction⁵² is that whatever a person focuses on will be brought into that person's existence, because the thought becomes directed energy which attracts those things upon which the mind is focused. If a judge\lawmaker focuses on the injustice, more injustice will come. In short, "You bring about what you think about".

It was after the 1970s that these ideas became more popular. Physicist Fritjof Capra wrote the book *The Tao of Physics*, which compared quantum mechanics with the principles of Eastern mysticism, thoughts also expressed in the 1979 book *The Dancing Wu Li Masters* by Gary Zukav. In 1985, physicist Nick Herbert wrote *Quantum Reality: Beyond the New Physics*, which discussed various interpretations of quantum theory, and in 1995, *Elemental Mind: Human Consciousness and the New Physics*, drawing on the notion that consciousness is a fundamental process of nature. In 1988, Deepak Chopra's book *Quantum Healing* described the power of the mind to heal the body on a cellular level by tapping into the "intelligence" that lies in every cell. Dr. Emoto's studies reveal the power of positive intention.⁵³ And in 2004, the movie *What the Bleep Do We Know* offered up a blend of quantum physics, spirituality, neurology, and molecular biology in documentary form to explore the relationship between quantum physics and consciousness.

We should pay attention to judicial discretion, the cornerstone of court's activity to make it "alive" to get the justice achievable. We should pay attention to legal creativity.

Attention is an important moment in every trial, in every case, in every legal issue because it creates a language inside a judge/lawyer, which allows him/her to listen to what surrounds him/her, to send\attract the energy. Language which we have already defined as discretion, as creativity. Discretion/creativity is a language of energy. One becomes capable of listening, one becomes receptive. This is the way to nourish the interiority of anyone. And if a trial seems unjust, it is a judge who does not know how to achieve justice, and the secret that it contains. "If thoughts can do that to water, imagine what our thoughts can do to us." – from the movie 2004, "What the Bleep Do We Know?"

Discretio est discernere per legem quid sit justum-⁵⁴if the reader remembers.

Willigis Jäger says: "Attention is the starting point and heart of all spiritual paths. A careful life is founded on the recognition that reality can only be experienced in the here and now".⁵⁵ The philosopher Edmund Husserl⁵⁶ speaks of the "light" of attention, emphasizing the spiritual value of this ability.⁵⁷ Simone Weil⁵⁸ attaches great importance to attention as

52 We mean the Law of Attraction and Quantum Physics. The Law of Attraction teaches that we attract into our lives whatever we focus on.

53 <https://www.goodtherapy.org/blog/mindfulness-matters-dr-emoto-studies-reveal-power-of-positive-emotion-012914>

54 Discretion is the selection of that which is just by the law.

55 Jäger Willigis, *Timeless Wisdom The secret behind all paths to spirituality*, (2010)

56 Husserl's thought profoundly influenced 20th-century philosophy, and he remains a notable figure in contemporary philosophy and beyond.

57 See in: https://cfs.ku.dk/summer-school-2017/background-readings/Text_Jacobs_2010_revision_2016_.pdf

58 Simone Adolphine Weil (3 February 1909 - 24 August 1943) was a French philosopher, mystic, and political activist.

the way to ecstasy. She writes: “the highest ecstasy is the attention at its fullest.”⁵⁹ In the chapter on attention in the *Principles of Psychology*, William James⁶⁰ writes what on a first reflection might sound rather plausible: “Millions of items of the outward order are present to my senses which never properly enter into my experience. Why? Because they have no interest for me. My experience is what I agree to attend to.”⁶¹ That is, according to James here, justice judge achieves is justice receives his attention or interests him and therefore becomes, is, or remains the object of his experience. In James’s words: “Only those items which I notice shape my mind – without selective interest, experience is an utter chaos. Interest alone gives accent and emphasis, light and shade, background and foreground – intelligible perspective, in a word.”⁶² If, as James would have it, to experience always involves attention or interest that makes discernment possible, then it seems that to experience amounts to being awake.

For exercising just discretion\creativity, a judge\lawyer has to be awake.

Here *Awakening* is not a metaphor: basic wakefulness is the effects of Buddhist meditation practices.

Mindfulness meditation has a long-standing history in Eastern practices that has received considerable public interest in recent decades. These practices have become a topic of widespread interest in both science and medicine, also. Mindfulness-based stress reduction can often help people address stress, chronic pain, cancer, anxiety, depression, and other chronic issues.

Mindfulness-based injustice reduction can often help judges\lawmakers address injustice.

In our papers (previous and present) we’ve been discussing the concept of mindfulness and describe its implementation in achieving justice/good lawyering as the treatment of injustice/bad lawyering; in achieving well-being as the treatment of stress; in achieving peace as the treatment of war and crisis. In an attempt to counterbalance the plethora of data dealing with effects and implementation of interventions of Buddhist meditation, we aim to provide evidence of meditation’s arousing or wake-promoting effects by drawing both from Buddhist textual sources, from legal and scientific studies.

Awakening is a complex problem.

The study published in *Physical Review Research*⁶³ is potentially applicable to humans (to a judge\lawmaker). The research team studied the brain signals produced by 13 fruit flies both when they were awake and when they were anesthetized. They then analyzed the signals to see how complex they were. “We found the statistical complexity to be larger when a fly is awake than when the same fly is anesthetized,” the team said. This is a major problem in justice, where it is crucial to differentiate between sleeping judges and those who are awake. “The study is significant because it highlights an objective way to measure conscious arousal, based on well-established ideas from complexity theory,” the team said. “It is potentially applicable to humans — and it reflects a growing interest in new theories of consciousness⁶⁴ that are experimentally testable.”

59 The Notebooks of Simone Weil (1951).

60 William James (January 11, 1842 – August 26, 1910) was the "Father of American psychology"

61 William James, *The Principles of Psychology*, Volume I, New York : Dover Publications Inc., 402-403 (1890).

62 Ibid

63 *General anesthesia reduces complexity and temporal asymmetry of the informational structures derived from neural recordings in Drosophila* by Roberto N. Muñoz, Angus Leung, Aidan Zecevik, Felix A. Pollock, Dror Cohen, Bruno van Swinderen, Naotsugu Tsuchiya and Kavan Modiay, 22 May 2020, *Physical Review Research*.

64 Consciousness is to be awake, *inter alia*. <https://franciewhite.com/consciousness-cosmology-physics-definitions-terms-for-beginners/>

This is especially important in the study of judiciary, judicial and law changes, and lawmakers\lawyers, where complexity theory can offer insights into how courts\lawyers become more just (fair), accessible, sustainable, adaptive, and innovative.

It sic, thought is the ultimate product of the evolutionary process and it is subject to evolution so it can continually improve. Edgar Morin⁶⁵ says: "Thought must establish frontiers and cross them, open concepts and close them, go from the whole to the parts and from the parts to the whole, doubt and believe, it must reject and fight the contradiction but, at the same time, it must take charge and nourishment ". And he continues: "Thought is an uninterrupted dialogic dynamism, a navigation between Scylla and Charybdis⁶⁶ towards which it drags every hegemony of one of the antagonistic processes".

May there be this awareness when a lawyer\judge uses his thoughts! "Those who act with approximation also get used to speaking with approximation, and coarse, imprecise and slovenly speaking also involves thinking in this indeterminacy [...] Being precise and clear in one's thoughts is the pledge of spiritual freedom".⁶⁷

We share the idea of Thomas Merton⁶⁸ that *spiritual life* is not intellectual life. It is not just thought. And of course it is not even a life of sensation, a life of feeling and experiencing the things of the spirit and the things of God. But the spiritual life does not exclude thought and feeling. It needs both. It is not a life from which mind, imagination and body are excluded. If it would be so, only few people could experience it. And again, if such would be the spiritual life, it would not be a life at all. If a man is to live, body, soul, mind, heart and spirit should be alive. Everything must be elevated and transformed by the action of spirit.⁶⁹ Spirituality concerns matters that transcend the physical/material world, such as the "soul" or "spirit" while mindfulness, by its definition, does not. While one can be a mindful person and a spiritual person, mindfulness simply means paying attention to the present moment, on purpose, non-judgmentally. One can be mindful, observing their surroundings in the present moment, without being spiritual.

William A Tiller⁷⁰ is convinced that men's mind can evolve so that it can influence men's daily life, and even physically change reality. Obviously, these are ideas that sink into the quantum theory of reality. Thoughts can change reality. Thoughts of a judge/lawyer, incorporated in judicial discretion/legal creativity, manifested in decisions/legal solutions, change the reality.

The psychoenergetic science inaugurated by Tiller⁷¹, assuming the ideas of Quantum Theory, essentially states that human consciousness and physical reality influence each other, and the sense of physical life is to learn about oneself, others and the world.

We enagurate energy in law, assuming the ideas of Quantum Theory, essentially state that human (legal) consciousness (mindfulness) presents in a State (society) and physical reality

65 Edgar Morin, pseudonym of Edgar Nahoum (1921), is a French philosopher and sociologist. He is known for the transdisciplinary approach with which he deals with a wide range of topics, including epistemology.

66 Scylla and Charybdis, in Greek mythology, two immortal and irresistible monsters who beset the narrow waters traversed by the hero Odysseus in his wanderings described in Homer's *Odyssey*, Book XII.

67 Florenskij Pavel A, *Letters from the Gulag* (English Edition), (6 Nov. 2020)

68 Thomas Merton (1915 -1968) was an American Trappist monk, writer, theologian, mystic, poet, social activist, and scholar of comparative religion. On May 26, 1949, he was ordained to the priesthood and given the name *Father Louis*. He was a member of the Abbey of Our Lady of Gethsemani, near Bardstown, Kentucky, living there from 1941 to his death.

69 More details Thomas Merton. Thoughts in solitude, <https://www.monasterovirtuale.it/pensieri-nella-solitudine.html>

70 William A. Tiller is emeritus professor of Science and Engineering of Materials, at Stanford University. Tiller spent 34 years in academia, after having been a consultative physicist at Westinghouse Research Laboratories for nine years, he has published over 250 scientific papers.

71 <https://brainworldmagazine.com/adventures-outlier-explorer-interview-william-tiller/>

of a State (society) influences each other. Consciousness of a State, of a court, of a legal firm consists of consciousnesses⁷² of its members. They are all one. Everything is connected.

We need *Mindfulness, Discretion/Creativity* to step justice/good lawyering up, not shut it down. We call on judges/lawyers to courage to change. However, it can be understood only by those who are ready to break away from the past. The world needs judges/lawyers who look ahead and are open to the future that is calling us.

We are optimistic the lawyers will be demanded, we aren't worried about the escalating war for staff talent⁷³, because mindful lawyer is a lawyer with high values, following the words of great Piero Calamandrei⁷⁴: "Many professions can be performed with the brain and not with the heart. But not the lawyer. The lawyer cannot be a pure logician, nor an ironic skeptic. First of all, the lawyer must be the heart. He is an altruist, someone who knows how to understand other people and make them live in themselves. The lawyer takes on their pains and feels their ambitions like his own. The lawyer is a profession of understanding, dedication and charity. This is why we love lawyer toga: we would like that, when the day comes, this black rag is placed on our coffin: to it we are fond of because we know that it has served to dry some tears, to relieve some headache, to repress some abuse: and above all to revive in human hearts the faith in the winning justice, without this faith the life does not deserve to be lived".

The current challenges, the ecology crisis, COP26, COVID-19 pandemic consequences are requiring lawyers\judges to make profoundly important decisions/legal choices which often have immediate impacts on our rights and freedoms and which will fundamentally shape our society and economy for years to come. Robust scrutiny and debate will improve the quality of these decisions and strengthen public trust in them. Questions from the audience are welcomed as we explore what it would be the next steps for future negotiations.

72 - the thoughts and feelings, collectively, of an individual or of an aggregate of people; in:

<https://www.thefreedictionary.com/consciousnesses>

73 <https://www.reuters.com/legal/legalindustry/attorney-recruitment-fears-temper-law-firms-bullish-outlook-2021-11-16/>

74 Piero Calamandrei (1889 – 1956) was an Italian author, jurist, soldier, university professor and politician. He was one of Italy's leading authorities on the law of civil procedure.